

Pentecost

also known as "Sa"

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Secondary source

Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

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Entry tags: Melanesia, Religious Group, Oceanic Religions

The Pentecost (Sa) are those native to the area of what is now the southern part of Pentecost Island, Vanuatu, Melanesia. Note that in this entry, the term "Pentecost" refers to the southern Pentecost. For the Pentecost, contact with Europeans and the arrival of Missionaries began in the late eighteenth century. Despite the long presence of the Roman Catholic Church and the Church of Christ, not all Pentecost were converted to Christianity; at the time this entry focuses on, 130 of the 400 Pentecost people were non-Christian. Principal ethnographic authority, Robert B. Lane (1965:250), notes that "the non-Christian population consciously maintains a relatively unaltered aboriginal culture, albeit with reduced flourish owing to diminished population and to contact with Europeans." Following Lane, this entry focuses on the remaining aboriginal culture, specifically in the village of Bunlap around the time of 1953. At this time, the Pentecost were horticulturalists, with patrilineages serving as the main social and political unit. High-ranking men (initiated males possessing greater age, experience, and magico-religious power) held both political decision-making power as well as ritual knowledge. Full-time religious practitioners were not present, but those with more magical (gurian) knowledge and power had the semi-professional status of ritualists and sorcerers. Mythology centers on culture heroes and sib (lineage) ancestors, as well as supernatural beings. Supernatural beings are present, but not described in substantial ethnographic details. They include spirit-beings of three types: *armat en sanga* (incorporeal beings capable of assuming human form), *lipsipsip* (malicious dwarf-creatures), and ghosts. Concerning ceremonies and rituals, the rites of *lo sal* are "one of the most important institutions of South Pentecost culture" (Lane, 1965:269-270). These rites consist of a man giving sacrifices of pigs, gifts, and/or payments to the members of his mother's and wife's sib. A man presents these gifts throughout his life, and the cycle continues with the birth of a son. Lane (1965:251) makes the important observation that "the people of South Pentecost recognize no category of culture comparable to that which we label religion, nor do they have any institutions which are primarily religious. The phenomena dealt with here permeate much of the culture." Consequently, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with society itself.

Date Range: 1928 CE - 1959 CE

Region: Southern Pentecost Island, Vanuatu

Region tags: Oceania, Melanesia, Vanuatu

Southern Pentecost Island, Vanuatu ca. 1953.
Specifically, the village of Bunlap.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: Cross-cultural codes 4. *Ethnology*, 11(4), 436-464.
- Source 3: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: Cross-Cultural Codes 3. *Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-295.
- Source 1: Murdock, G.P. (1967). *Ethnographic Atlas*. Pittsburgh, PA: University of Pittsburgh Press.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=oo17-002>
- Source 1 Description: Lane, Robert B. "Melanesians Of South Pentecost, New Hebrides." *Gods Ghosts And Men In Melanesia; Some Religions Of Australian New Guinea And The New Hebrides*, Oxford University Press, 1965, pp. 250-79.
- Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=oo17-004>
- Source 2 Description: Lane, Robert B., and Barbara Savadkin Lane. Unpublished Field Notes. [s. n.], 1957

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "European contact began late in the eighteenth century and led to a rapid decline in population. Missionary activities commenced almost at the time of contact, but conversion to Christianity is not yet complete. The present population totals about 400 persons of whom 130 are non-Christians" (Lane, 1965:250).

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: "Two mission groups are important in South Pentecost, the Roman Catholic Church and the Church of Christ. Catholic missionaries have discriminated against aboriginal beliefs and practices selectively, incorporating, tolerating or forbidding in accordance with their judgement as to the compatibility of particular features of native culture with Catholic dogma and European values. The Church of Christ missionaries have followed a policy of forbidding or discouraging any beliefs and practices associated with what they believe to be the native magico-religious system or which appear to them to be in conflict with European-Christian morality" (Lane, 1965:277).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, indicates that the Pentecost were pacified before the

twenty-five-year ethnographic present (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, indicates that the Pentecost were pacified before the twenty-five-year ethnographic present (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that the Pentecost would recruit new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: This entry considers the Pentecost religious group to be coterminous with Pentecost society at large. "The people of South Pentecost recognize no category of culture comparable to that which we label religion, nor do they have any institutions which are primarily religious. The phenomena dealt with here permeate much of the culture" (Lane, 1965:251).

Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

Notes: Priests are not present among the Pentecost.

Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of religious infrastructure.

Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: There is neither a singular head of the polity, nor a singular head of the religion.

Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

Notes: The Pentecost do not have clearly defined religious officials (see Lane, 1965:275-276). However, high-ranking men hold both political decision-making power (making them political officials) as well as ritual knowledge. Consequently, political officials can be loosely considered equivalent to be religious officials. "High-ranking men control sib knowledge, which includes power and ritual, and in addition they are demonstrated possessors of great personal power" (Lane, 1965:273).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 130

Notes: "The present population totals about 400 persons of whom 130 are non-Christians. The bulk of the latter live in four villages near the east coast. The non-Christian population consciously maintains a relatively unaltered aboriginal culture, albeit with reduced flourish owing to diminished population and to contact with Europeans. The materials considered in this study, unless otherwise specified, are drawn from an essentially functioning aboriginal culture" (Lane, 1965:250-251).

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 33

Notes: Lane, 1965:250-251

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: "There are no religious specialists qualitatively set apart from the rest of the population. Everyone has more or less of a grasp of the essentials of religious belief and practices and everyone can more or less act for himself in his own religious life. Quantitative differences exist. Some people have so much more knowledge, skill and power that others solicit their services. High men in the graded society might be classed as specialists, but their special knowledge accrues because of their position in the social structure and not because they are qualitatively different" (Lane, 1965:275-276).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of scriptures.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of monumental religious architecture.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of monumental religious architecture.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "Every human being has a soul, but ideas regarding its nature are not clearly formulated...The soul is most often described as an amorphous image of the exterior body. There is disagreement as to when the soul enters the body. This difference of opinion may reflect Christian influence, since Christian and younger non-Christian informants claim that it is in the body at birth, whereas older informants claim that it is acquired after birth. Assuming that the latter idea is the aboriginal belief and since the soul can leave the body during life, it seems reasonable to say that the soul maintains rather than activates life... After death the soul, particularly if it remains in or returns to this world, is called aramaet, a 'ghost'" (Lane, 1965:255-256).

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Lane, 1965:255-256

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: Lane, 1965:255-256

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "The underworld is the land of the dead" (Lane, 1965:263).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

Notes: Lane, 1965:263

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

Notes: "The underworld is the land of the dead" (Lane, 1965:263).

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: "There is uncertainty regarding the derivation of the soul. In some cases the soul is that of an ancestor. Such reincarnations may be recognized because the individual exhibits physical or mental traits like those of the ancestor. When an infant cries incessantly, it is assumed to be a reincarnation. The parents name ancestors until the infant hears his original name and ceases to cry. That name is then given to him again. In other cases the fact of reincarnation never becomes evident" (Lane, 1965:255).

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: Lane, 1965:255

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that reincarnation is believed to occur in animal/plant form.

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that reincarnation is believed to occur in the form of inanimate objects.

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Burial practices are not described in the principal ethnographic authorities (Lane, 1965; Land

and Lane, 1957).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Burial practices are not described in the principal ethnographic authorities (Lane, 1965; Land and Lane, 1957).

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Burial practices are not described in the principal ethnographic authorities (Lane, 1965; Land and Lane, 1957).

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Burial practices are not described in the principal ethnographic authorities (Lane, 1965; Land and Lane, 1957).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "Spirit-beings are timeless phenomena. They are not frequently met with, although they may appear anywhere and are believed to be fairly numerous...In a casual way, spirit-beings are categorized. The most common type are *armat en sanga*. They are light coloured and incorporeal and are usually encountered in lonely places. They may assume human form and seduce people, death resulting from such encounters. Another type, perhaps as common but more malicious than deadly, are *lipsipsip*, dwarfs who dwell in trees and in stones. Usually they ignore human beings, but if offended they may cause injury to people or to their belongings. They are cannibalistic and if sufficiently aroused or hungry will kill and devour human beings. Ghosts are conceptually spirit-beings especially when they remain, as some do, in this world" (Lane, 1965:264).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a supreme high god. Additionally, SCCS Variable 238, High Gods [note, equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 34] indicates that a high god is absent or not reported (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Ghosts are conceptually spirit-beings especially when they remain, as some do, in this world. The line between human beings and spirit-beings becomes blurred at some points. A man of highest rank in the graded society transcends human limitations and could as well be

classed as a spirit-being. A sorcerer with shape-shifting abilities is not far removed from a supernatural being" (Lane, 1965:264).

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– I don't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– Yes

Notes: "In a casual way, spirit-beings are categorized. The most common type are *armat en sanga*. They are light coloured and incorporeal and are usually encountered in lonely places. They may assume human form and seduce people, death resulting from such encounters...Another type, perhaps as common but more malicious than deadly, are *lipsipsip*, dwarfs who dwell in trees and in stones. Usually they ignore human beings, but if offended they may cause injury to people or to their belongings. They are cannibalistic and if sufficiently aroused or hungry will kill and devour human beings" (Lane, 1965:264).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

Notes: "Another type [of spirit-being], perhaps as common but more malicious than deadly, are *lipsipsip*, dwarfs who dwell in trees and in stones. Usually they ignore human beings, but if offended they may cause injury to people or to their belongings. They are cannibalistic and if sufficiently aroused or hungry will kill and devour human beings" (Lane, 1965:264).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Culture heroes and sib (lineage) ancestors are present and important, but appear to only exist in mythology (Lane, 1965:265-266). "The culture heroes were essentially human but they differed from modern human beings in virtue of their complete possession and control of such attributes as power, sacredness and virility. For this reason they had capabilities far beyond those of modern men" (Lane, 1965:266). "The line between human beings and spirit-beings becomes blurred at some points. A man of highest rank in the graded society transcends human limitations and could as well be classed as a spirit-being. A sorcerer with shape-shifting abilities is not far removed from a supernatural being" (Lane, 1965:264).

Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "Spirit-beings are timeless phenomena. They are not frequently met with, although they may appear anywhere and are believed to be fairly numerous...In a casual way, spirit-beings are categorized. The most common type are *armat en sanga*. They are light coloured and incorporeal and are usually encountered in lonely places. They may assume human form and seduce people, death resulting from such encounters. Another type, perhaps as common but more malicious than deadly, are *lipsipsip*, dwarfs who dwell in trees and in stones. Usually they ignore human beings, but if offended they may cause injury to people or to their belongings. They are cannibalistic and if sufficiently aroused or hungry will kill and devour human beings. Ghosts are conceptually spirit-beings especially when they remain, as some do, in this world" (Lane, 1965:264).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of supernatural monitoring.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of supernatural punishment.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of supernatural rewards.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of an eschatology.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of castration.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: "...one of the important institutions of South Pentecost culture, the rites of lo sal...The rites consist, for a man, of sacrifices of pigs and presentation of gifts or payments on public and ritual occasions to members of his mother's sib and the sib of his wife. Throughout his life a man presents mats and pigs to his mother's brothers. From the time of his engagement until the birth of his first child, he periodically makes gifts of pigs and mats to his wife's parents. After the birth of his child, a man gives pigs and mats to his wife's brothers, the mother's brothers of the child, thus starting a new cycle which the child will continue throughout his lifetime. When the man dies, his son periodically gives pigs to the mother's brothers of the deceased. Thus, when the son is immature the father provides the necessary gifts to the mother's brothers of the child. When the father is deceased the son reciprocates by providing sacrifices to the mother's brothers of the father" (Lane, 1965:269-270).

To other in-group members:

– Yes

Notes: Lane, 1965:269-270

To out-groups:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of regular meetings/services/prayer.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– I don't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose

one):

– A tribe

Notes: "The society is theoretically subject to another society with an alien culture, e.g., to a colonial power, but is in fact essentially unadministered by the latter and thus enjoys a de facto autonomy" (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; Column 1: Political Autonomy). SCCS Variable 237 (note, equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 32), Jurisdictional Hierarchy Beyond Local Community, indicates that the Pentecost have no levels of political authority beyond the local community (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Although there are no levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the community, the Pentecost can be considered to be a tribal society based on the presence of non-centralized, but part-time "officials", usually being experienced, older men. Additionally, patrilineal sibs (e.g., "lineages whose core membership normally comprises residents of more than one community") are present (Column 20: Patrilineal Kin Groups and Exogamy; Murdock, 1967). "Society consists of sibs, villages, an indefinite surrounding world of known extra-local kin and apart from these, strangers who were always potentially dangerous and viewed with suspicion" (Lane, 1965:268). "Political organization is weak and nebulous in South Pentecost. In theory, in any village all initiated males have a say in any decision affecting the group. However, within the general framework of equality, seniority is influential. The components of seniority are age, experience and power, the combination of which inevitably adds up to high rank in the graded society. The expression of this influence is a potential and there is great individual variation in its use. Some high men openly exercise their authority but most wear a cloak of humility and dignified preoccupation, their concern being ideally devoted to matters beyond the ken of ordinary men. They prefer to work through others from behind the scenes" (Lane, 1965:273).

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: A formal bureaucracy is not present among the Pentecost. See question on levels of social complexity, above.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: "Police functions are not specialized or institutionalized at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery" (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; Column 10: Police)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: "Supreme judicial authority is lacking at any level above that of the local community" (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; Column 9: Judiciary).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: "They are horticulturalists depending on their crops, taro in particular, and upon products of the forest for their major sustenance" (Lane, 1965:250).

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: The Pentecost rely predominantly on horticulture for subsistence. Gathering, fishing, and animal husbandry supplement the diet. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.